

5G RAN resource slicing with flexible functional splits over multi-tenant environment

Michail Dalgitsis*, John S Vardakas[†] and Christos Verikoukis[‡]

*Dept. Signal Theory and Communications (TSC), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain

[†]Iquadrat Informatica S.L., Barcelona, Spain

[‡]Dept. Computer Engineering and Informatics (CEID), University of Patras, Greece

Abstract—5G is set to be revolutionary and more flexible compared to the previous mobile network generations able to support services with diverse requirements. However, the wide range of use cases poses challenges to network resource allocation and management. Infrastructure providers to address the issues deriving from the requirements of a multi-service environment, adopt two key paradigms, network slicing and functional split options, in which the former controls the network resources and the latter relaxes the fronthaul constraints. Since the slices are deployed over a common and shared infrastructure functional split must dynamically adjust the demands of the service providers. As there is no one-split-fits-all option, we propose a mathematical framework for the optimal selection of functional split options per slice requests and the optimal slice size in terms of data-rate, that maximizes the infrastructure provider’s total profits. Hence, a thorough analysis is performed and the optimal solutions are discussed with a comparison against hybrid network configurations.

Index Terms—Network slicing, Flexible functional split, Fronthaul, Multi-tenancy, Cloud RAN, Resource management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cell densification became a favourable solution to millimeter wave frequencies reserved by 5G networks, and centralized cloud RAN (CRAN) emerged as a key architecture to efficiently embrace this solution by separating all the baseband processing functions (BPFs) to a central location leaving the cells with simplified radio units (RUs) [1]. Although with CRAN architecture infrastructure providers (InPs) are experiencing pool gains in terms of resource management, operational expenditures and capital expenditures, the fronthaul (FH) links consume excessive bandwidth comparing to the user data rates they support, giving birth to new levels of centralization namely functional split (FS) options [2].

The FS type decides how many base station functions to leave locally close to the user, with relaxed FH requirements (bandwidth, delay) and how many functions to centralize with the benefit of shared resources. As 5G new business model introduced a wide range of use cases with diverse requirements, there is no one-split-fits-all option [3], and a flexible functional split (FFS) approach is introduced, in which BPFs can be distributed dynamically and flexibly between FH units [4].

Such flexibility could be enabled by two 5G drivers, software-defined networking (SDN) and network functions virtualization (NFV), softwareizing and virtualizing respec-

tively the network architecture and management plane, to create enhanced communication capabilities and resource optimization techniques [5]. Specifically, SDN makes networks programmable by separating the control and data planes improving the flexibility of network function management and efficiency of data transfer and keeping track of the available resources in the radio and optical part. In the meantime, NFV aims to virtualize network functions, for example, in virtual machines. Therefore, the functions can be moved to different locations, and the corresponding virtual machines can be migrated to run into general purpose hardware.

Through SDN and NFV, the concept of network slicing (NS) was proposed to tackle the issues that have arisen from the myriads of 5G use cases, by dividing one physical network into multiple logical networks, referred to as network slices [6]. Acknowledging the benefits of NS, InP’s adopt slicing techniques in order to support new-age services, allowing new profit opportunities by virtualizing its resources and sharing them among different tenants or service providers (SPs). However, the profit opportunities associated to the slice market need to be reconsidered in order to evaluate resource allocation, admission control and pricing policies [7].

The existing approaches do not take into account joint NS and FS techniques in calculating the total InP’s profits. The optimal placement of BPFs affects the maintenance network costs (like energy costs) and the optimal slice size configuration affects the profits earned by selling slices to tenants. Thus, a novel slice-oriented cost model is needed in order to explore the slice-split relationship, along with meeting the requirements of diverse traffic services simultaneously.

In this paper, we propose a mathematical framework for the optimal selection of FS options among SPs, who share a common infrastructure and request slices with heterogeneous requirements, as well as the optimal selection of slice size in terms of service data-rate, aiming to maximize the total profits of InP. Hence, our contributions are summarized as follows:

- A CRAN scenario is proposed maximizing InP’s total profits, while meeting the diverse 5G requirements by assigning separate virtualized BPF chains to each service-based network slice, involving a central office (CO) on the edge, small cells with RUs on the access, and a multi-tenant service environment. Each SP (or slice tenant) then uses these slices to provide its services to end users.

- The slice management procedure of the InP is formulated, as a profit optimization problem targeting the FS paradigm, in addition to slice prioritization, revealing the relationship between NS and FS together with the trade-offs among different metrics.
- A heuristic algorithm is applied, to find the optimal placement of the FS options, as well as the optimal slice size configuration in order to maximize InP's total profits, considering radio, optical and computational resources in the radio link, FH link and CU/RU elements respectively.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a discussion of the related work. Section III introduces our 5G resource slicing deployment framework with FFS. Section IV describes a quantitative slice pricing model based on tenants' requirements and network configuration and propose a heuristic algorithm to address the problem through a flowchart representation. Section V showcases the experimental setup and the evaluation results. Finally, Section VI provides a conclusion of this work and our future intentions.

II. RELATED WORK

FS, acting as a promising 5G paradigm in the CRAN architecture, has been focus of research during the last years. On one hand, many studies addressed centralization degree maximization problem, by exploiting FFS on a cell-centric FH, where either all distributed units (DUs) are configured with the same FS under the connected CU [8] or each DU can receive its own split [9] based on the network's performance.

On the other hand, studies on centralization savings, considering slice-centric splits also have emerged. For example, in [10], a joint RAN slicing with FFS is proposed, optimizing the centralization degree and throughput. However, splits are assigned in advance based on the service characteristics and do not change dynamically in case there is a system failure or update. Moreover, the work in [11], presents a functional split per slice approach, maximizing centralization benefits on different slice granularity levels. However, the performance metrics, centralization degree and migration costs are not well-defined and there is room for improvement. In [12], the authors demonstrate a per user split approach that jointly optimizes and orchestrates heterogeneous resources. The split decision is occurring on user basis, which is a fine-grained slice approach, in which each user represents a slice. Although the experimental results outperform cell-centric methods, it can be challenging for practical implementations. Also, in [13], authors focused on the RAN slicing architecture for the main 5G service categories, choosing an appropriate functional split option, considering the points of bandwidth consumption on the FH and communications latency. Although experimental results show that the specific performance of the slices is advantageous for each service type, slices do not share the same RU but instead authors considered dedicated RUs for each slice on their testbed. All the aforementioned functional split per slice works leverage the SDN and NFV capabilities for the construction of slices and the dynamic allocation of BPFs.

Fig. 1: System model

Nevertheless, none of those works research the relationship between the slice management and split configuration in order all the network players who own or use the resources to be benefited.

The appropriate admission control and management of the slice requests problem has received attention recently and works [14]–[16] formulate slice pricing models with InP to sell oriented service-based slices to SPs, upon the latter's requests. The network profits occur from the total revenue earned by the granted slices minus the losses either from the rejected slices or the slices which does not meet the service level agreement (SLA). However, the impact of the FS option is not an objective here as all frameworks consider a distributed RAN architecture. Hence, aiming to analyse the impact of the appropriate split selection of the slices, we design a heuristic algorithm, which receives on-demand slice requests over a CRAN architecture and outputs the right slice management and configures the network dynamically with the right splits in order to maximize InP's profits.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

Fundamental aspects of 5G RAN flexible architecture is the cloud FH network segment with the internal protocol layer functional decomposition the CU/DU/RU split, as proposed by 3GPP [2]. In this work, we consider the reference architecture shown in Fig. 1 where several DUs are deployed in the cell station room, integrated with RUs as DUs/RUs, and are connected to the CU through a fiber link. In what follows, the DUs/RUs are referred as lightweight RUs with some intelligence, equipped with general processors to perform part of the baseband processing alongside with transmit/receive signals capabilities and the corresponding optical network unit (ONU), while the rest of the baseband processing of many small cells takes place in the CO, which is connected to the optical line terminal (OLT). The optical network is utilized as fiber to the cell infrastructure to provide dedicated mobile services (such as broadband, IoT) to multiple tenants in order to avoid any degradation to fixed user services.

Tenants provide services to end users by requesting service-based slices from the InP, who owns both the optical and radio network. Each slice request has specific requirements and each granted slice reserves a portion of the total resources. Radio, optical and computational resources are sliced accordingly by the InP, who also monitors the recourse availability and decide whether to accept a slice request, or reject it and scale it down with corresponding penalties. Within this context,

TABLE I: Service providers requirements of slice requests

Requirement	Description
SLA type	Strict, Flexible
Data-rate	Required data-rate in Mbps
Holding time	Slice duration in hours
Coverage	Set of RUs

multiple service instances of multiple tenants are represented as different logical SPs.

A. Tenant-based slice model

Whenever an SP requests a slice, an SLA is specified stating the terms for the pricing and customization. In other words, each SLA defines both the quality of service to be guaranteed and the payment of a fee that the SP should provide to the InP during its permanence in the system. This action generates revenues to InP by leasing network slices. However, every time the InP rejects a request because resources are not enough or scales down a service to serve more tenants, a penalty must be paid, leading to reduced revenues for the InP. We consider two types of services, for example, services with strict SLA and services with flexible SLA. A strict service (e.g., mobile online gaming, real-time process control) comes with strict data-rate requirements and if the InP scales down the slice while the service is active, InP violates the SLA and a penalty should be applied. A flexible service (e.g., video streaming, file transfer) on the other hand, comes with flexible, non-strict data-rate constraints, with the required data-rate ranging between a maximum and minimum value. In this case, InP delivers best-effort service from the contracted range. As a result, penalties occur when InP scales down below the minimum value, making this service type more flexible and less costly compared to the other type. Each generic slice request is defined by its SLA type, its data-rate requirement DR, its holding time H_t and its slice coverage represented by a set of RUs and Table I summarizes the requirements of SPs.

B. Split-based slice operation policy of InP

To achieve FFS to different slice request by SPs, InP rely on SDN and NFV technologies. Specifically we extend the baseline RAN architecture with SDN controllers located in the CO, with various roles such as, an inter-slice controller, an optical and radio bandwidth allocation performer, and a split decision-maker. The latter runs an FFS as a service (FFSaaS) application on the northbound interface, who keeps track of the slices, the radio resources, and the available bandwidth on the optical FH with collaboration to slicing and resource controller respectively, to assign appropriate FS per slices. The rest of the communication with the RAN can be maintained over the southbound interface. In the meantime, as in [12], we extend the NFV concept into the RAN protocol stack, decomposing the baseband chain into microservices which are instantiated into containerized network functions to perform either cell or slice processing tasks. As a result, BPFs can be dynamically and flexibly distributed between CU and RUs.

Fig. 2: Reserved resources from a slice reply

The FS options can be broadly classified as either a high layer split (HLS) containing the PDCP, RLC and MAC functions or a low layer split (LLS) containing PHY and RF [2]. We consider the three out of the eight most researched options proposed by 3GPP, to cover both HLS and LLS, namely option 2 (PDCP-RLC split), option 6 (MAC-PHY split), and option 8 (PHY-RF split). The InP taking into account the available FS options replies to an accepted or scaled down slice request with the reserved resources, as it is shown in Fig. 2. In this figure, the slice reserves a number of resource blocks from the radio link translating into the required data-rate and based on the FS option it reserves an amount of bandwidth in the fiber link and computational resources in the CU and RU. Slice provision and maintenance consume energy from the corresponding infrastructure, thus, we declare as network costs the energy costs needed to operate the slice instances.

IV. A HEURISTIC ALGORITHM FOR RAN SLICING WITH FLEXIBLE FUNCTIONAL SPLITS PER TENANT

In this section, we formulate the flexible split per slice (FSpSlice) management problem. We first describe the slice pricing and energy cost model, in which the InP generates its profits and expenditures and afterwards we detail the problem formalization based on the aforementioned models. Finally, we present a heuristic algorithm through a flowchart representation.

A. Problem formulation

The profits the InP makes by the tenants' slice requests are estimated based on SLA characteristics. As two types of SLAs are considered, the InP differentiates the services with a gain factor GF , which is higher compared to the flexible service, to describe a more costly service, thus producing more revenues. However, when the InP scales down the data-rate requirement of a slice, it must pay a price which is proportional to a penalty factor PF . As the InP has the right to reject a newly arrived slice request while ongoing slices are active, the PF is smaller in the rejection case than in scaling down case, where an SLA has already been stipulated. These cases result in the InP's losses and the estimated profits the InP makes by providing slice instances are given by:

$$PR_{slices}^{InP} = REV_{slices}^{InP} - LOS_{slices}^{InP} \quad (1)$$

where REV_{slices}^{InP} are the revenues the InP earns by the slice requests and LOS_{slices}^{InP} are the losses coming from service

degradation or slice rejection. More in detail, REV_{slices}^{InP} is given by:

$$REV_{slices}^{InP} = \sum_{slices} GF * DR_{req} * W * Ht * c_{data} \quad (2)$$

where GF is the gain factor to differentiate the revenues among services, DR_{req} is the required data-rate of each tenant in Mbps, W is a weight variable which takes value 1 if resources are enough, otherwise scales down accordingly with data-rate degradation, Ht is the holding time in hours that shows the duration of each slice, and c_{data} is the cost of data service (in monetary units per MB). In addition, LOS_{slices}^{InP} is given by:

$$LOS_{slices}^{InP} = \left(\sum_{slices \in S} PF_{sd} * \Delta DR * Ht + \sum_{slices \in R} PF_{rej} * DR_{req} * Ht \right) * c_{data} \quad (3)$$

where S is the set for the degraded slices, R is the set for the rejected slices, PF_{sd} and PF_{rej} are the penalty factors for the scaling down and rejection cases respectively and ΔDR is the data-rate difference from the minimum required to the finally given data-rate. In the strict-SLA case the minimum requirement is the same as the requested data-rate.

In order to quantitatively study the network costs to serve and maintain the slices, we express them as the energy costs coming from the infrastructure components, and divide them into fixed and variable costs. To this end, the total power consumption is given by:

$$P_{total} = P_{fixed} + P_{variable} \quad (4)$$

where P_{fixed} is the fixed and $P_{variable}$ the variable power consumption. The fixed power consumption is computed as:

$$P_{fixed} = P_{CO} + P_{optical} + P_{RF} \quad (5)$$

where P_{CO} is the power consumed in the CO for cooling and SDN processing related activities, $P_{optical}$ is the power consumed from OLT and ONUs and P_{RF} is the power consumed from RF interface and equal to $P_{RF} = (P_{int} + P_{ampl} * N_{users} * N_{tenants})$, depending on the interface's power P_{int} , the number of tenants $N_{tenants}$, the number of users N_{users} and amplifier's power factor P_{ampl} . Variable power consumption derives from fronthaul link and virtualized BPFs, thus:

$$P_{variable} = P_{FH} + P_V \quad (6)$$

An LLS consumes more bandwidth and generates constant FH load with the trade off less computational costs and power consumption. On the other hand, an HLS is characterized by relax FH requirements but no pool gains in the CO. Therefore, the FH power consumption and the virtualized processing depend on the split options and can be derived as, respectively:

$$P_{FH} = \left(\frac{\sum_{tenants} FH_{load}}{R_{fiber}} \right) * P_{fiber}^{max} \quad (7)$$

$$P_V = \left(\sum_{tenants} VP \right) * P_{server} \quad (8)$$

where FH_{load} is the total FH load of the tenants' data-rate requirements generated based on the FS option, R_{fiber} is the data-rate in the fiber link, P_{fiber}^{max} is the maximum power consumption per fiber link, while regarding the virtualized power, VP is the total virtualized baseband processing of all tenants based on the model in [17] multiplied with the power a server consumes. Consequently, the total energy costs can be derived as follows:

$$CO_{energy}^{InP} = E_{total}^{kWh} * c_{energy} \quad (9)$$

where E_{total}^{kWh} is the total energy expressed in kWh issued by P_{total} and Ht , and c_{energy} is the cost per kWh.

Besides, as detailed in [18], the estimated bandwidth per slice on the FH link, is calculated as follows:

$$FH_{load}^{option2} = a_1 * DR_{slice} * b_1 \quad (10)$$

$$FH_{load}^{option6} = (a_2 * DR_{slice} + a_3 * N_{users}) * b_1 \quad (11)$$

$$FH_{load}^{option8} = a_4 * BW_{slice} \quad (12)$$

where the coefficients a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , a_4 are constants and refer to signalling information from PDCP header encapsulation, signalling information from MAC header encapsulation, scheduler overhead per user, and radio configuration (e.g., sampling rate, number of antenna ports, channel bandwidth), respectively. It is worth noting that each split in 5G new radio is multiplied by a scaling factor b_1 based on the reference scenario. DR_{slice} corresponds to the service traffic load, and BW_{slice} to the slice bandwidth.

Our aim is to maximize InP's total profits, PR_{total}^{InP} , considering radio, optical and computational resources in the radio link, FH link and CU/RU segment, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximize: } & PR_{total}^{InP} \\ \text{subject to: } & \sum_{slices} DR_{req} \leq R_{cell} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{slices} FH_{load} \leq R_{fiber} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{where: } PR_{total}^{InP} = PR_{slices}^{InP} - CO_{power}^{InP} \quad (15)$$

The first constraint denotes that the total radio resources of all slices on the access site must not exceed the maximum achievable cell throughput. The second constraint means that the total generated FH load of all slices on the optical site should not exceed the total fiber link capacity. The objective function aims to find the optimal placement of the FS options as well as the optimal slice size configuration in order to maximize InP's total profits.

B. Algorithm description

The above illustrated problem can be solved by applying the algorithm shown in Fig. 3. The proposed algorithm takes as input the slice requests from different tenants and initially checks if the radio resources are enough in order to serve the tenants with the requested data-rate. If resources are not enough due to the reservation of already ongoing active

Fig. 3: Flowchart for the proposed algorithm

slices, a slice management strategy begins and iterates over all possible data-rate slice combinations to find one desired by all served and newly arrived tenants. At each iteration it evaluates both the revenues and the losses that can appear by scaling down a service. Also, at each slice data-rate combination it iterates once more to evaluate all different available functional split options, to choose the split that meets the FH constraints and minimizes the power consumption bringing the highest centralization benefits. Once the slice-related profits and energy-related costs to maintain a slice are calculated, the optimal combination of slices in terms of data-rate is selected as output. In case the radio resources are enough, the InP accepts the new slices and selects the optimal split that minimizes its energy costs.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND RESULTS

In this section, we report the performance of our FSpSlice approach. We start by describing the environment setup. Then, we define the performance metrics considered to evaluate our strategy and analyze the results, and we discuss the effectiveness of our proposal compared to relevant CRAN frameworks. In fact, we consider hybrid architectures with static/dynamic slicing and split as baselines for performance analysis. In this context, three approaches are evaluated: dynamic slicing (DS) with static split per slice (DS+SSpSlice), static slicing with flexible split per slice (SS+FSpSlice), and static slicing (SS) with static split per slice (SS+SSpSlice). Static slice refers to the admission control of slices, when there are not enough resources the slice request is rejected, while static split means that all slices of an RU have the same split. For the performance evaluation of the different considered mechanisms, experiments are conducted in MATLAB environment.

A. Experimental setup

In line with the formulation of Section IV, we consider a CRAN architecture having one RU connected to the CU via an optical FH link of 1 Gbps. We assume that both the CU and the RU have enough computational capacity to serve all the slice requests coming from tenants. Also, we assume 4 tenants sharing the infrastructure of InP, of which two request services

TABLE II: System parameters

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
Scaling down step	10 Mbps	P_{ONU}	5 W
c_{data}	0.003 €/MB	$P_{\text{fiber}}^{\text{max}}$	2 W
c_{energy}	0.1 €/kWh	P_{int}	2 W
P_{CO}	200 W	P_{ampl}	0.13
P_{OLT}	20 W	P_{server}	84 W

with strict SLA of 80 Mbps and 50 Mbps data-rate, respectively, while the other two have flexible requirements ranging at 50-40 Mbps and 50-20 Mbps. We recall that penalties occur, when InP cannot guarantee the required and minimum data-rate for the strict and flexible cases, respectively. We set the GF to 1.5 for strict and to 1 for flexible SLA services and the PF to 1.5 and 1 for the scaling down and rejection strategy, respectively. Moreover, the holding time of slice requests are exponentially distributed with mean holding time to 1 hour. Finally, we set 10 users for each slice, where resources are scheduled equally among them, c_{energy} to 0.1 €/kWh, c_{data} to 0.003 €/MB, and we configure the radio with 20 MHz channel bandwidth, 2x2 MIMO scheme, 64QAM modulation format and zero numerology. The remaining fronthaul parameters are $a_1 = 1.0013$, $a_2 = 1.006$, $a_3 = 1.5$ Mbps, $a_4 = 98.3$ bps/Hz and the rest of the system parameters are illustrated in Table II, in which the optical power values are taken from [19].

B. Evaluation results

Prior the discussion of the results, alongside with InP's profits we define one more performance metric, the energy efficiency (EE) as the ratio of the total FH load in the expense of the power consumption in the network. Thus in Fig. 4a we measure the total profits of the InP. We notice the resources are not enough to serve all 4 slice requests. With efficient resource allocation and the aim to maximize its total profits, InP accepts all the requests in expense of service degradation. It can be seen that slices with strict SLA are intact, while flexible slices are offered to their tenants with decreased data-rates. We demonstrate the slice sizes in terms of data-rates for the three most optimal solutions. The first and the second solutions result in the same payments, which, however are increased compared to the payments related to the third solution. The first and the second solutions though, differentiate in the split options per tenant as depicted in Fig. 4b. The requested and the finally delivered data-rate affect the selected split option. In addition, these solutions generate different FH loads, resulting in another EE. The third optimal combination intends to degrade a strict SLA tenant favoring the rest, to create a higher FH load, and make the system more energy-efficient. Fig. 4c shows for various numbers of users per slice the higher EE that is provided by the third optimal solution. This trade-off between the total profits and the EE proves that appropriate split must be assigned to each slice.

To investigate more the split-slice relationship, we measure again the total profits among hybrid architectures. As it is shown in Fig. 4d dynamic slicing results in higher payments than static mechanism, in which one slice was rejected due

Fig. 4: Performance evaluation

to insufficient resources. However, the DS+FSpSlice, similarly to DS+SSpSlice architecture, generates the same profits because the energy costs that depend on flexible splits are very low due to the short slice life. Fig. 4e illustrates the FS options per tenants among the four different architectures. When there is an FFS mechanism, LLS is assigned to tenants to benefit from centralization gains. We present the EE as one of the centralization benefits in Fig. 4f, with DS+FSpSlice outperforming the rest of the approaches.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a heuristic algorithm for dynamic slice management in a 5G network, in line with FFS architecture. The illustrated results show on one hand a slicing technique for network resource management, accepting all the slice requests versus the non-optimized cases with rejections, and 6% profit increase by optimally degrading only the flexible services. On the other hand, we showed benefits of 6% and 327% in terms of profits and energy efficiency, respectively, over alternative hybrid solutions. Finally, for future work, we intend to investigate delay-sensitive service requests together with intra-PHY splits, to evaluate the latency requirement and the higher centralization benefits, respectively.

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